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PERCEPTIONS OF MULTIMODAL ONLINE INSTRUCTION DURING NATIONAL LOCKDOWN: EXPLORING THE BLENDED CONTINUUM

Frikkie George¹, Ekaterina Rzyankina²

Cape Peninsula University of Technology, South Africa

¹georgef@cput.ac.za; ²rzyankinae@cput.ac.za

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ABSTRACT

In the context of a global pandemic, education at most universities in South Africa is undergoing rapid adaptation and transition to online, blended learning. Tertiary educators are expected to adapt to flexible schedules, changing pedagogical practices, and learning and work environments shaped by technology. The COVID-19 pandemic has made it increasingly important for institutions to migrate their traditional face-to-face (F2F) instruction methodology to fully online teaching and learning. Educators and institutions have urgently had to adapt to a 'new normal' that responds to the demands of the global crisis. A new approach is perhaps essential to address the learning needs and challenges of currently enrolled first-year students, who are obliged to study in varying environments yet still need to progress equally toward attaining a high-quality qualification.

This case study determines educators' and students' perceptions of multimodal online instruction and learning and the experience of first-year engineering students transitioning from F2F to online multimodal teaching and learning. The study, in this way, explored the efficacy of transition to online multimodal teaching and learning across the F2F-online continuum. The first-year University of Technology (UoT) engineering students were exposed to both face-to-face and online multimodal teaching and learning environments. The data collected were analysed both qualitatively and quantitatively. The findings indicate that the students performed better when exposed to multimodal online instruction than when exposed only to face-to-face classroom instruction. The study also found that the students and lecturers positively perceived online multimodal teaching and learning.

INTRODUCTION AND RATIONALE

The current pandemic caused by the novel coronavirus disease of 2019 (COVID-19) makes it increasingly important for educational institutions to adapt their instructional methodologies to address the challenges experienced by educators and students. Numerous studies show that many educators do not effectively use the technological

resources at their disposal (Karimzadeh, et al., 2017; George et al., 2012; Appana, 2008). There also seems to be a prevailing assumption that face-to-face instruction can be directly translated into an online format (Mdlongwa, 2012; Churton, 2008). The main focus of this paper is to explore the various modes of instruction to which students were exposed pre-and post-national lockdown due to the COVID-19 pandemic. This study used the blending with purpose model based on the blended learning conceptualising framework of Picciano (2009). It spans the continuum of instruction from face-to-face (F2F) in the classroom to entirely online and provides both the foundation for the study and a lens through which its findings are viewed. The mere presence of a device does not denote a habit of study digitally, and educators need greater clarity on the functionalities of devices and how different profiles of students utilise them. Nevertheless, there is a legitimate concern that as the millennial generation enters university in more significant numbers, there will be a need to accommodate technology-savvy students taught by technology-literate educators (Picciano, 2009).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Online instruction, in general, has many benefits over face-to-face instruction, which include increased access, improved quality of learning, better preparation of students for a knowledge-based society, and the opportunity for 'lifelong' learning (Appana, 2008). Nevertheless, despite the ever-increasing popularity of online instruction, there are limitations to its ability to replicate features of a traditional F2F classroom environment, such as social interaction, prompt feedback, engaging activities, instructional flexibility, adaptation to individual needs and immediacy (Larreamendy-Joems & Leinhart, 2006). Frymier's (1993) research concluded that students who began a course with low to moderate motivation to study had increased motivation to study after interacting closely with an effective instructor, while students with a high level of motivation were unaffected by a high level of immediacy.

The term multimodal instruction means different things to different people. In the broadest sense, multimodal instruction encompasses a "wide variety of technology/media integrated with conventional, face-to-face classroom activities" (Picciano, 2007). Multimodality refers to communicative situations that rely upon combinations of different 'forms of communication to be effective. "Multimodal" itself denotes a mixture or combination of modalities. The mix can be a course comprising both F2F and online components. In this study, multimodal instruction is contrasted with the traditional talk-and-chalk classroom instruction and the combination of different modes of instruction and learning, enabling new affordances of learning and choices. The concept and application of multimodal learning will be explored in this paper based on the Blending with Purpose model illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Adapted Blending with Purpose model

The Blending with Purpose model depicts the various modes of instruction, including conference platforms, social media, a learning management system, WebAssign and phone. This model posits that instruction is not always about learning content or skill but can also be about supporting students socially and emotionally. Social and emotional development is an important part of anyone's education, especially for students in their first year of study. They may frequently need someone to speak with, whether to help them understand a complex concept or provide advice on career and professional opportunities.

METHODOLOGY

This case study used a mixed-methods approach to collect data from marine engineering science students and lecturers. Questionnaires comprising questions answerable according to a 5-point Likert scale and six structured questions were used to collect data from a purposive sample of 10 lecturers and 36 students, probing the perceived usefulness and ease of use of technology, technophobia, and the availability of and access to multimodal online teaching and learning.

Figure 2 illustrates the transition in the continuum from face-to-face to online instruction experienced by the educator and students, based on the blended learning conceptualisation framework of Picciano (2007).

Figure 2: Adapted blended learning conceptualisation framework (Picciano, 2007)

The educator and students used the Blackboard Learning Management System (LMS) for instruction and learning, utilising various functionalities such as text, video and audio. Students submitted six assignments. The teaching and learning for the first three assignments took place primarily in a F2F environment (left quadrants in Figure 2), and the teaching and learning for the last assignments took place in a predominantly online environment (right quadrants of Figure 2). All the assignments were standardised to be of a similar degree of difficulty, covering the following topics: Matrices, Trigonometric functions, Exponential functions, Complex numbers, Vectors and Derivatives.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Perceptions and accessibility of online multimodal instruction and learning

Gardner (1983) posits that “intelligence is not a singular entity but is made up of multiple entities in different proportions used by individuals to understand and to learn about the world.” Gardner’s work also addresses the concern that too much teaching and learning is linguistically-based (reading, writing, speaking) and that the other intelligence needs to be better utilised using a multimodal instruction approach. Figures 3 and 4 illustrate the students’ and educators’ perceptions of online multimodal instruction and learning, respectively.

Figure 3: Students' perception of multimodal online learning

The students' responses, as set out in Figure 3, evince a generally positive perception of multimodal online learning. This observation is based on the responses to Questions 1 (skill deficit), 2 (interest) and 3 (reliability). The data bears out the notion that younger students are “digital natives” who use technology most comfortably (Prensky, 2001). However, it is noteworthy that most of the students indicated a preference for face-to-face lectures rather than online lectures (Question 5). This might be attributed, at least in part, to “cabin fever” and/ or “online learning fatigue” because of the prolonged national lockdown and students' need for social and emotional interaction. The students also indicated that the course content was too demanding for the multimodal online learning format alone, and many students found it challenging to manage “cope” with the workload (Questions 5 and 6).

Figure 4: Lecturers' perception of multimodal online learning

Figure 4 indicates that the overall responses for Questions 1 (skills), 2 (interest) and 3 (reliability) on the part of the lecturers were positive towards online multimodal instruction and learning. The lecturers' responses also suggest that they have ready access to online multimodal instruction facilities and support (Question 4). However, most of the lecturers found that most of the course material was not online-friendly (Question 5), and students struggle to deal with it online (Question 6).

When the students and lecturers' responses are compared, it can be seen that they both express positive perceptions but feel that the course material is not always adaptable to the online format and that most students could not keep up with the workload and pace of online instruction. This observation could be attributed to the unpreparedness of content and lecturers and students' new online learning experience. While the students expressed reservations about the reliability and the accessibility of online instruction and learning, their educators felt otherwise.

Observations during instruction

The first part of the study involved observation of face-to-face instruction for five weeks. Students were seated at desks, with the lecturer conducting the lesson at the front of the classroom. The instruction methodology involved mainly question-and-answer and taking notes from the board. Occasionally students had group discussions with peers next to them. The assignment scripts and the assessment thereof were pen-and-paper based. The latter part of the study focused on online multimodal instruction. The lessons were conducted using the online conferencing platform, Zoom. Students were divided into breakout groups on the online platform to discuss specific problems with peers and share their responses in the main virtual

room with all the participants. The lecturer and students used online multimedia Google Docs/ Forms, WhatsApp and email for asynchronous engagement outside of the online sessions, illustrated in Figures 5 and 6.

Figure 5: Engagement on WhatsApp

Figure 6: Google form for feedback

The students also used an e-textbook with the WebAssign online platform for self-study, submission of assignments and assessment. During both the face-to-face and online instruction, the educator used dialectic questioning to probe students' knowledge (Black & William, 2009). The educator also used the Dialogical Argumentation and Assessment for Learning Instructional Model (DAAFLIM) to stimulate discussion and constantly assess students' progress, thereby ensuring that they were responsive to the teaching and learning process (George et al., 2019). Students used a threaded electronic discussion board during online lessons to take part in the presentations and provide responses. Figure 7 represents a screenshot during an online lesson on vectors.

Whiteboard - Zoom

$\vec{A} = 2i - 3j + k$
 $\vec{B} = 4i + j - 3k$
 $\vec{C} = -i + j - 3k$

a) $(\vec{A} \cdot \vec{B}) \cdot \vec{C}$
 $= (2 \cdot 4 + (-3) \cdot 1 + 1 \cdot (-3)) \cdot (-i + j - 3k)$
 $= (8 - 3 - 3) \cdot (-i + j - 3k)$
 $= 2 \cdot (-i + j - 3k)$
 $= -2i + 2j - 6k$

b) $\vec{A} \cdot (\vec{B} \times \vec{C})$
 $= \begin{vmatrix} i & j & k \\ 4 & 1 & -3 \\ -1 & 1 & -3 \end{vmatrix}$
 $= i(1 \cdot (-3) - (-3) \cdot 1) - j(4 \cdot (-3) - (-3) \cdot (-1)) + k(4 \cdot 1 - (-1) \cdot (-3))$
 $= i(-3 + 3) - j(-12 - 3) + k(4 - 3)$
 $= 0i + 15j + 1k$
 $= 15j + k$
 $\text{scalar} = -(-12 - 3) = -(-15) = 15$
 $= -40$

Figure 7: Screenshot of a Zoom presentation of a lecture on Vectors

During this lesson, the lecturer assessed the students' conception of the vector and scalar product. The problem was shared with the students before the online session to solve on their own. During the online session, the whiteboard was shared with the students who worked collaboratively to solve the problem. Students used different colour annotations and the microphone to contribute and explain their understanding/solution of the problem. All the students can provide their responses in a chat-box, which the lecturer used to stimulate discussion. After the lesson, the students provided feedback via Google Jamboard; one of the responses was, "I loved the interaction of the other students, they made the session lively!"

Table 3: Comparing assignment scores in F2F and online environments

Statistics	F2F environment			Online environment		
	Ass. 1 Ave score (%)	Ass. 2 Ave score (%)	Ass. 3 Ave score (%)	Ass.4 Ave score (%)	Ass. 5 Ave score (%)	Ass. 6 Ave score (%)
Mean	36 (60%)	34 (57%) 35.7 (59%)	37 (62%)	35 (58%)	40 (67%) 39.3(66%)	43 (72%)
Difference	3.6 (6%)					
N = 36; Maximum score of assignments = 60						

Table 3 compares the students' performance scores in assignments conducted during face-to-face and online multimodal environments. The mean scores of the different teaching and learning formats indicate that the students performed better in the online environment, with an average difference of 6%. Closer analysis reveals that the students' performance increased gradually over time for both environments, with the exception of Assignment 1. The gradual improvement of assignment scores in both environments can probably be attributed to the fact that students gradually acquire familiarity with a particular mode of instruction. However, the steady improvement appears to be greater during the online environment. Therefore, it is reasonably safe to conclude that the overall difference in performance during the F2F and online environments can be attributed to the innovative online multimodal teaching and learning approach.

IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This paper compared the F2F and online multimodal teaching and learning environments in terms of students' performance. The data show that the online multimodal environment produced better results in learning compare to F2F learning. Therefore, it is suggested that some key elements employ various modes of online teaching explicitly and deliberately in the classroom. Online multimodal teaching is, of course, not limited to the engineering mathematics classroom and can profitably be introduced in other disciplines. This paper has not attempted to develop concrete strategies for teaching mathematics, instead, the paper should be read as an invitation to engineering educators who teach mathematics to consider the potential of the multimodal approach presented here and to more complex mathematical problems during online activities. The paper provides the basis for understanding the potential of online multimodal learning modes for teaching abstract and calculation-based subjects such as mathematics.

CONCLUSION

This study will prove of interest to researchers interested in supporting national STEM education reform efforts, particularly those interested in designing innovative instructional methodologies for implementation on both a small and a large scale. Moreover, the study provides a tangible example of how online multimodal teaching can help teachers evaluate their students' knowledge-in-use and ensure that it is

coherent with learning objectives, both in the classroom and in a virtual setting. This approach has profound implications for how educators organise their instructional methodologies to support learning.

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